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ANALYSIS OF THE DYNAMICS OF TECHNOLOGICAL INDICATORS OF OPERATING WELLS BASED ON A SYSTEMATIC APPROACH

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ABSTRACT

To assess the feasibility of operating the well stock in various ways, it is necessary to take into account both the economic efficiency of their work and the presence of a hydrodynamic connection between them.

The technical and economic profitability limit of well operation is the level of costs, taking into account energy-resource, technical potential, above which operation is inappropriate in today's market conditions.

In the process of developing and operating oil fields, one often has to deal with unforeseen conditions and the impossibility of fully formalizing (justifying) the decision to select and carry out the necessary geological and technical measures.

Taking into account the above, the authors propose an approach for processing array of field data based on statistical methods. This approach will help to make a prompt and substantiated decision on the management of the existing well stock.

Keywords: oil reservoir, well stock, emergence, gas lift fund.

1. Introduction

The relevance of the work lies in the fact that the effective management of the existing well stock will help reduce energy costs and optimize their work. The purpose of the work is to develop an analytical method for analyzing a data array, which will help make substantiated decisions on managing well operations and choosing the necessary geological and technological measures, which, in turn, will increase the efficiency of the oil recovery process while minimizing economic and energy costs [1, 2].

Production and technological schemes of the oil production process require constant regulation of well operation modes and carrying out the necessary studies in order to promptly redistribute potentially excessively high energy costs.

An oil deposit, together with wells and all communications, is a complex dynamic system, for the design, analysis and management of which new approaches based on the principles and methods of the theory of large systems are needed.

It is also known that, in accordance with the principle of emergence, according to which a large system cannot be uniformly described accurately, different methods and models are required for its analysis at different levels, the conventional deterministic approach to describing the processes of field development and

production is necessary, but far from sufficient and essential limiting control options. There are two main trends in this:

- elements of the TP management system are considered as their generalization and systematization into a logically complete, integral system of management and regulation of development processes;

- another direction is to consider the process of management, monitoring and regulation of technological processes as a local system.

As an example, this paper considers the dynamic state of the technological indicators of the stock of operating wells in the Gum Deniz field (information courtesy of SOCAR).

2. Methodological part

The problem is considered on the basis of the information array of technological indicators of the gas-lift well stock, where one of the main sources of costs is non-compliance with regime parameters due to the deviant behavior of the reservoir system and transient fluid and gas dynamic processes.

As one of the methods of production intensification, the timely regulation of well operation modes is increasingly used. With the use of IT-techniques and technologies, modern volumes of this technological process no longer require an individual (for individual wells) approach to its implementation, but an analysis

of the entire production system (site analysis) as a whole.

The efficiency of technological processes implies the presence of a certain technological and economic balance between the various parts of the overall system. As a result, along with assessing the state of the system as a whole, it is necessary to analyze the change in its individual parts (subsystems) in order to timely regulate their work according to the principle of composition and decomposition. Since the category of processes under consideration is dynamic and subject to both purposeful and random changes over time, an important role is played by the choice of such methods of analysis that would ensure the efficiency of assessments.

As such a method, in [2] it is proposed to group production wells according to their contribution to the total production in accordance with the principle of hyperbolic distribution.

Within the high- and low-productive zones of the reservoir, identified when grouping wells according to the law of hyperbolic distribution, periodically changing in-situ processes can develop. To determine the nature of these processes, the method of evolutionary modeling is used, which makes it possible to determine what type of evolutionary process dominates in the operation of oil and water wells with or without saturation.

Determining the types of the model and their combinations for oil and water for each well makes it possible to identify groups of wells where it is possible to successfully carry out technical and economic measures to control the selection [1]. At the same time, it is necessary to take into account the periodic transition of wells from one group to another, which is adequate to Markov processes with certain final probabilities that determine the possibility of estimating the boundaries of technical and economic indicators.

3. Results and discussion

This method of grouping wells in combination with clustering based on the law of hyperbolic distribution makes it possible to identify groups of wells at large field facilities where it is possible to successfully carry out measures to regulate the selection, taking into account the nature of the development objects and to obtain the total effect from large-scale measures to regulate.

The proposed method was tested in the analysis of the state of the well stock of the Gum-Daniz field.

The entire gas-lift well fund is grouped according to the Pareto principle (Fig. 1).

The situation shown in figure 1 can be the initial basis for the selection of wells for the regulation and evaluation of the results of ongoing geological and technical activities.

As can be seen, the curves for the flow rate of liquid, water, oil and the flow rate of injected gas are well straightened in logarithmic coordinates, i.e. $\log R - \log Q$. On all graphs, two sections are distinguished, one of which characterizes "high-rate wells", the second - combines "low-rate wells".

In addition, there is also a third section characterizing the intermediate state. As a result of applying this

approach, the entire gas-lift fund is classified into three groups of wells: Group I, characterized by oil flow rate $Q_o < 2$ t/day; Group II, characterized by a flow rate of 2 t/day $< Q_o < 5$ t/day; Group III, characterized by a flow rate $Q_o > 5$ t/day.

The reliability of such clustering is also confirmed by grouping by gas extraction and consumption of the compressed working agent.

Below, in order to identify the consistency of the analyzed parameters for the whole field, the coefficient of consistency of rankings (oil, water, gas sampling and compressed gas flow) with each other is used, the consistency coefficient w is used [4]:

$$w = \frac{12 \sum_i D_i^2}{m^2 (n^3 - n)} \quad (1)$$

In the presence of related ranks, the concordance coefficient w ($0 < w < 1$) is calculated by the formula:

$$w = \frac{12 \sum_i D_i^2}{m^2 (n^3 - n) - mB} \quad (2)$$

$$\text{where } D_i = \sum_{j=1}^m R_{ij} - \frac{\sum_j \sum_i R_{ij}}{n} \text{ at}$$

$i = 1, 2, \dots, n; j = 1, 2, \dots, m$ is the sum of the ranks assigned to all values of the analyzed parameters of the i -th serial number of the observation, minus the average value of the sum of the ranks; m - number of wells; n is the number of observations; $B = \sum_{k=1}^z (B_k^3 - B_k)$;

B_k is the number of related ranks for $k = 1, \dots, z$.

The verification was carried out using the same rank values as in the construction of the Pareto distribution.

Obtained results are the following

$$m = 4, n = 90, B = 0, \sum D_i^2 = 503900, w = 0.518.$$

To determine the reliability of the significance of the concordance coefficient w , the value χ^2 is used

$$\chi^2 = m(n-1)w \quad (3)$$

which is compared with the critical value taken from the known χ^2 distribution table, $f = n - 1$ degrees of freedom and significance level $\alpha = 0.05$. When $\chi^2 > \chi_{table}^2$ the hypothesis of consistency can be accepted. If $\chi_{table}^2 = 112$ at $\chi^2 = 184$, therefore, the analyzed parameters of the operating fund - the extraction of oil, water, gas and the flow rate of compressed gas at the level of the value of the Kendell concordance coefficient equal to 0.518 in this case are consistent with each other, while it is possible to increase the degree of consistency (up to $w = 1$) of these parameters by adjusting the operating modes wells [5].

The proposed approach can be applied in the technical and economic assessment of the potential of hydrocarbon deposits, regardless of the method of their exploitation [4, 6].

Fig. 1. Gas-lift well fund grouped on the basis of the Pareto principle (oil, water, gas production and compressed gas volume)

It is known that a well, its near-wellbore zone and part of the reservoir between wells are interconnected and interacting elements of a single techno-natural system.

When assessing the technical and economic feasibility, underestimation of the features and degree of influence of the near-wellbore zone as one of the elements of the system leads to a general decrease in the efficiency of oil and gas field development. When comparing the distribution of the analyzed parameters by wells before and after the regulation process, the new distribution, if successful, should be higher than the previous ones. In addition, the angles of the straight lines should indicate an increase in the characteristic index. The growth of the characteristic index indicates that the distribution of the analyzed parameter becomes more uniform.

Another feature of gas-lift operation of wells is the presence in the gas coming from the well to the surface of not only working, but also a significant amount of its own (reservoir) gas, which, as well as technological, is involved in the work of lifting the liquid, i.e. has a certain (both positive and negative) effect on the operation of the gas lift. This circumstance makes it necessary to take into account own (reservoir) gas when constructing control dependences (characteristic curves) for flooded wells operated by gas lift. Therefore, when constructing them, it is necessary to use as an argument such a parameter as the flow rate of the separation gas (containing a fraction of the formation gas), and not the working gas, as is usually accepted for gas-lift wells [1, 3].

Conclusions

The proposed approach makes it possible to make a prompt and justified decision based on the analysis of the available information and its processing using statistical criteria. The described technique provides the conditions for making a decision on the effective regulation of the operation of the existing well stock, choosing the most optimal geological and technological measure aimed at optimizing the operation of the object. In addition, effective management of the operating mode of the existing well stock reduces economic and energy costs in the process of field development. These aspects are of particular importance in the development of non-Newtonian oil fields in offshore conditions.

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